

LIC AGENT PROFESSION FOR FEMALE - A STUDY

S. Karthikeyan* & Dr. M. Mahalakshmi**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

LIC agent profession is a communicative job. It is not easy. In this field one works hard to get success and achieve his target. Some planetary positions helps one to sign as the best LIC agent and gives him/ her a lot of money as commission. Saturn, Jupiter, Mercury are very important planets help to sign as the best LIC agent. Similarly second bhava, seventh bhava and eighth bhava help to sign as the best LIC agent. We can see this elaborately

Key Words: LIC Agent, Profession, Saturn, Mercury, Jupiter, Second Bhava, Seventh Bhava, Eighth Bhava

Jupiter:

Jupiter is the planet for money. Money gives us pleasure. We live in the world to earn money. Money is very important for us. In LIC agents horoscope, Jupiter has a vital role. If Jupiter is weak, it doesn't give money.

Saturn:

Saturn is the karaga planet of life. In Tamil it is called Ayul karaga. Insurance is done for save life. If we meet an accident the insurance Policy will help us. So, Saturn plays a vital role in LIC agent's horoscope.

Mercury:

Mercury is the communication planet. It is also for friends and partners. Mercury gives social interaction. We can easily attract friends through the help of Mercury. So, Mercury is very important for LIC agents.

Second Bhava:

It is called Money bhava and also speech bhava. LIC agents earn money from commission through their customers by their attractive speech. They should explain the benefits of the certain policy and canvass their clients very well. Second bhava is also important for teachers, astrologers and lawyers.

Seventh Bhava:

It indicates our customers and also society. If this bhava is good in our horoscope we can easily attract our friends and spouse. If this bhava is not good one is always isolated from others. For LIC agents to earn Money customers are must. So, this bhava helps LIC agents to attract customers.

Eighth Bhava:

This bhava indicates our life span. Howmany years we should live on earth? It indicates the passive income. More LIC agents work in another sectors. They have done this as a part time job. Eighth bhava also indicates the unexpected money. If the policy holder die, his family members will get unexpected money. So, eighth bhava is more important bhava to the LIC agents.

Who becomes the Best LIC Agent?

There are six common rules for becoming the LIC agent

Rule Number 1:

Mercury should standing 1/4/7/10 or 1/5/9 from Saturn (kendra or triangle).

Rule Number 2:

Seventh House Lord should stand in kendra or triangle 1/4/7/10/5/9 place from lagna) or stand its own star.

Rule Number 3:

Second house lord should stand in 7/9/11 house

Rule Number 4:

Jupiter and Mercury combination through conjunction / aspect / next to touch.

Rule Number 5:

Mercury stands in Jupiter's star or Jupiter stands in Mercury 's star

Rule Number 6:

Mercury or Saturn stand in second or twelveth house from Jupiter.

Special Rule for Men:

Eighth bhava lord should stand or aspect the tenth bhava.

Special Rule for Women:

Mercury or saturn should stand in kendra (1/4/7/10) from Jupiter

Therefore totally seven rules make one the very best in LIC agent profession. Atleast two or three rules must be in their horoscope

Example 1:

Name : E. Jaya jothi
 Date of Birth : 10. 07.1969
 Time of birth : 9.37 am
 Place of birth : Trichy
 Moon dasa balance : 1 year 10 Months 10 Days

RAHU	SATURN	MOON VENUS	MERCURY SUN		VENUS	SUN	
	RASI				NAVAMSA		RAHU
			ASC				ASC SATURN
	MARS		KETHU JUPITER				MARS

Planet	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	Pooram	1	Simmam	Simmam
Sun	Punarvasu	2	Mithunam	Rishabam
Moon	Krithiga	3	Rishabam	Kumbam
Mars	Anusha	2	Viruchigam	Kanni
Mercury	Arudra	2	Mithunam	Makaram
Jupiter	Uthiram	3	Kanni	Kumbam
Venus	Rohini	1	Rishabam	Mesham
Saturn	Bharani	1	Mesham	Simmam
Rahu	Pooratathi	4	Meenam	Kadagam
Kethu	Uthiram	2	Kanni	Rishabam

How Our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Rule Number 3:

Second house should stand in 7/9house /11 house

In this horoscope the second lord stands in eleventh house. It is also his own house, very best one.

Special Rule:

Mercury stands tenth bhava from Jupiter. Kendra. Very best.

Totally two rules out of seven applicable in this horoscope

Example 2:

Name : **G. Rajalakshmi**
 Date of Birth : 09. 06.1963
 Time of birth : 07.00 am
 Place of birth : Madurai
 Moon dasa balance : 19 year 7 Months 16 Days

JUPITER		MERCURY VENUS SUN	ASC RAHU				RAHU MARS
	RASI				NAVAMSA		
SATURN			MARS				MOON SUN
KETHU MOON							SATURN

Planet	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	Arudra	1	Mithunam	Danush
Sun	Mirugasira	1	Rishabam	Simmam
Moon	Pooradam	1	Dhanush	Simmam
Mars	Magam	3	Simmam	Mithunam
Mercury	Karthigai	2	Rishabam	Makaram
Jupiter	Revathi	2	Meenam	Makaram

Venus	Karthigai	2	Rishabam	Makaram
Saturn	Avittam	2	Makaram	Kanni
Rahu	Punarvasu	3	Mithunam	Mithunam
Kethu	Uthiradam	1	Danush	Danush

How our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Rule Number 1:

Mercury should standing 1/4/7/10 or 1/5/9 from Saturn (kendra or triangle).

In this horoscope Mercury and Saturn stands as triangle.

Rule Number 2:

Seventh House Lord should stand in kendra or triangle 1/4/7/10/5/9 place from lagna) or stand its own star.

In this horoscope the seventh house lord. Jupiter stands in tenth house (Dasama Kendra)

Rule Number 3:

Second house lord should stand in 7/9/11 house

In this horoscope the second house lord Moon stands in Seventh house.

Rule Number 5:

Mercury stands in Jupiter's star or Jupiter stands in Mercury 's star

In this horoscope Jupiter stands in Mercury's star Revathi

Totally four rules out of seven applicable in this horoscope

Example 3:

Name : S. Narayani
 Date of Birth : 11. 06.1962
 Time of birth : 8.24 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Moon dasa balance : 1 years 11 Months 4 Days

	MARS	MERCURY SUN	VENUS	JUPITER			SATURN KETHU VENUS
JUPITER	RASI		ASC RAHU	MOON	NAVAMSA		MERCURY ASC
KETHU							SUN
SATURN			MOON	RAHU			MARS

Planet	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	Punarvasu	4	Kadakam	Kadakam
Sun	Mirugasira	1	Rishabam	Simmam
Moon	Uthiram	3	Kanni	Kumbam
Mars	Bharani	1	Mesam	Simmam
Mercury	Rohini	4	Rishabam	Kadakam
Jupiter	Sathayam	4	Kumbam	Meenam
Venus	Punarvasu	3	Mithunam	Mithunam
Saturn	Sravanam	3	Makaram	Mithunam
Rahu	Ayilyam	1	Kadakam	Dhanush
Kethu	Sravanam	3	Makaram	Mithunam

How Our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Rule Number 1:

Mercury should standing 1/4/7/10 or 1/5/9 from Saturn (kendra or triangle)

In this horoscope Mercury and Saturn stands in triangle position very best one.

Rule Number 2:

Seventh house lord should stand in kendra or triangle 1/4/7/10/5/9 place from lagna) or stand its own star.

In this horoscope, seventh house lord stands in own seventh house.

Rule Number 3:

Second house should stand in 7/9 /11 house

In this horoscope the second house lord sun stands in eleventh house.

Rule Number 4:

Mercury or Saturn stand in Second or twelveth house from Jupiter.

In this horoscope Jupiter and Saturn stands in 2/12 position. very best.

Special Rule:

Jupiter and Mercury combination through conjunction / aspect / next to touch.
In this horoscope Jupiter and Mercury stand in kendra position. Very best.
Totally five rules out of seven applicable in this horoscope

Conclusion:

From this research paper everyone easily check one's horoscope is apt for LIC agent profession. My sincere thanks to my HOD, Mrs. K. Jothimani Madam and also my research supervisor Mrs. Mahalakshmi Madam for their co-operation to finish this article successfully.

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